

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF THE INDIVIDUAL SITUATION IN THE STUDENT GROUP

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the socio-psychological factors that affect the state of a person in a group of students. Empirical research data on the establishment of relationships between different levels of the socio-psychological condition of students in the group and the predominant types of relationships between students are presented.

Introduction: Currently, social psychology is of great interest in the study of student groups in the system of higher professional education. Researchers emphasize the high relevance of these groups for its participants, especially the importance of interpersonal relationships within the group [1-4]. Each person who is the subject of interpersonal relations enters as a system of interpersonal relations, orientations, expectations determined by the joint activities of people and the content of their communication. in various social formations, including small social groups. Relationships in small social groups affect the effectiveness of joint activities, the nature of the communication process and are characterized by selectivity and emotional tones [5].

Analysis of literature on the topic. Research on the psychological study of student group status has been conducted overseas and in the United States. Galina Mikhailovna Andreyeva is a Soviet and Russian social psychologist and sociologist who defines a group as a person whose subjects are united by certain common features, including the nature of joint activities. Artur Alexandrovich Rean is a Russian psychologist and Yakov Lvovich Kolominsky. The data obtained in social psychology do not create a complete picture of determining status differences. The characteristics of students as subjects of communication can be interpreted from the point of view of the social state of development. The student period is characterized by a change in leading activities, a change in social status, and the entry of young people into a new social role. G.M. Andreeva [6] defines a group as a person whose subjects are united by certain common characteristics, including the nature of joint activities

Research methodology. Thus, a group is a group of people, which is characterized by the following characteristics: joint activity, structure, level of development, etc. activity is interconnected with dynamic processes within the group, perception of each other's subjects. Problems of groups and joint activities are traditionally considered in social psychology [1, 6-9]. But many issues, including the problem of the interaction mechanisms of the individual and

the group, require further research. One of the important characteristics of interpersonal interaction is the position of a person in a group or status, which means the position of a person in the system of interpersonal relations and the measure of his "psychological acceptability" by group members. It can be considered as a fairly objective indicator of the success of a person's communicative activity. Ya.L.Kolominsky [1] defines status as an integral concept, which includes both objective parameters, for example, a person's position in the intragroup structure, and a subjective reflection of his own position, reflected in different degrees. Thus, in modern social psychology [1, 9] status is considered as the subject's place in the system of interpersonal relations, which determines his rights, obligations and certain privileges in the group. It is common to distinguish between business leadership and emotional leadership. The role of the instrumental "business" leader consists of actions aimed at solving the tasks assigned to each participant and the entire group, and the role of the emotional leader is related to the emotional aspects of the group's relationships.]. Much of the work of researchers on the problem of sociometric status in groups was devoted to the study of the relationship between sociometric status and various individual typological characteristics, for example, extroversion, introversion, level of aggression, external attractiveness, school success, intellectual ma 014 information, age, etc. At the same time, A.A. Reana and Ya.L. Kolominsky the data obtained in social psychology do not create a complete picture of determining status differences. The available information is abundant and sometimes contradictory. The problem of individual status in peer groups has been studied more by researchers of child development, adolescence and young adulthood], such an important stage as "student age" has not been sufficiently studied in this regard. The characteristics of students as subjects of communication can be interpreted from the point of view of the social situation of development. The student period is characterized by a change in leading activities, a change in social status, and the entry of young people into a new social role. Adolescence is a special life stage that mediates a person's transition to adulthood. A student who has started an independent life is essentially not independent, he is often economically and psychologically dependent on his parents. Such a gap between the official beginning of social maturity and its actual "non-beginning" is a serious contradiction of this period of development. Student age is a stage for a person when this contradiction is resolved, active direction and development of new social functions takes place [6]. Staying as a student in a higher education institution involves the development of new competencies and new behavioral strategies. They are often associated with dominant, independent behavior. Students are characterized by a desire to control everything that happens around them in communication, to influence what others do, feel or think about them. They do not want to accept the influence of other people and obey them. characterized by the intensity of interpersonal interaction and the expansion of the social circle. Informal communication that optimizes the emotional state of a person and helps in difficult life situations is especially important for students. The need for recognition, self-respect and self-acceptance is clearly expressed [5]. Reference groups have a huge impact on students. A study by N.D. Tvorogova [4] showed that the level of importance of the group in which they are included is very important for students. The influence of information groups is especially great in relation to the satisfaction of basic needs for students: avoiding failure, maintaining a high position in the group, self-awareness and recognition of the individual by other members of the

group. avoid conflict between assessments. , the need for achievement, high status, group prestige, belonging and acceptance needs. The situation of social development in which students find themselves is very democratic, where spontaneity and sincerity are encouraged. The university system is more democratic than the school system, and the status of a student is similar to that of a school student. A sociometric procedure was used to determine the level of expression of different socio-psychological conditions of students in the group. The reliability of the obtained results was ensured by using a number of mathematical statistical methods, including the r-Spearman correlation coefficient. The computer program "SPSS 17.0 for Windows" was used for data analysis. Unlike usual, the sociometric procedure includes three criteria. Based on the criterion "with which member of your group do you like to spend your free time", the emotional state was determined. Business status was determined based on the criterion "which member of your group would you turn to for help with your studies." The status of "psychotherapeutic" was determined based on the criterion "Which member of your group would you turn to for advice when solving an important life problem?" The degree of expression of each type of socio-psychological condition was determined based on the sum of the accepted choices. Sociometric indices were calculated for each type of socio-psychological condition for each group member. Since the quantitative structure of the groups participating in the study was different, the socio-psychological condition was determined not by the absolute number of elections, but by individual sociometric indicators. Sociometric status indices of group members were calculated separately for all three types of socio-psychological status. Then, in the group of students participating in the research, finding the average value of the indices for the three types of status, the general index of the socio-psychological condition was determined, in addition, with the help of V. Stefanson's "Q-sorting" technique, students' superior relationships with each other were determined. This method allows us to determine the characteristics of interpersonal relations in the group according to the following parameters: "dependence - independence", "generality - intolerance", "acceptance of struggle - avoidance of struggle". In accordance with the objectives of the study, using the sociometric procedure, students with high, medium and low socio-psychological status were determined: emotional, business and "psychotherapeutic". Indicators of the socio-psychological condition of the students in the group by all types and the general index of the socio-psychological condition in the group were interpreted as follows: those who received an index of less than 0.10 are of low status, those who received an index from 0.10 to 0.20 are average status, indices were classified from 0.30 to higher status. The percentage of the weight of each socio-psychological status of students in the group was determined, and then using the Spearman r-correlation analysis procedure, we determined how correlated the expression levels of different types of statuses are. students in the group. The analysis of correlation relations showed that there are significant relationships between the three types of social-psychological status of students in the group. The higher the emotional state, the higher the business and "psychotherapeutic" status of the student in the group ($p \leq p0.05$; $p \geq p0.01$) and vice versa. Thus, the leadership structure in the studied groups of students is harmonious. Then, using the Spearman r correlation coefficient, the relationship between the existing relationships and the severity of different socio-psychological conditions was determined. A statistically significant, reliable correlation was found between business status and the attitude of "avoidance of war".

That is, most students who seek help with their studies prefer to avoid confrontation in interpersonal relationships, seek to avoid conflictual interactions, and maintain neutrality in group discussions. According to the study, what students with high sociometric status have in common, regardless of its modality (emotional, business and "psychotherapeutic"), is that they are successful communicators; they demonstrate better expressive abilities (including the ability to form their own opinions) than others. appearance), High-status students are characterized by high self-esteem. In addition, regardless of the degree of closeness of the relationship, high-status students are "significant others" for other students, meaning that they significantly influence the self-esteem of members of student groups.

A characteristic feature of modern student groups, according to researchers [2-4], is a certain dispersion of its participants (compared to previous decades). The reasons for such dispersion are: the increase of independent working hours, the possibility of using Internet resources during the educational process, the large number of working students, the loss of the traditions of organizing educational work in higher educational institutions, etc. However, The student group remains the most important institution of socialization of young people and influences the development of their personality. The sociometric status of a group member is an important component of the process of professionalization, because it often represents a relatively stable value and describes a person's relationship system, and is a criterion for a person's ability to develop a flexible behavior strategy in a group. and is an indicator of social adaptation in different living conditions. Researchers describing the age of students note that during this period, issues of professional education appear most acutely. self-determination, moreover, for many students, this period is associated with creating a family or establishing long-term, emotionally significant relationships. This is a period of serious crises, heavy burdens, worries and problems. So, in the process of professional education, the formation of a person not only as a subject of a profession, but also as a subject of interpersonal relations takes place, and in this regard, the place of the group of students, its position in the group. , the role of the subject in the system of interpersonal relations within the group is extremely large. Information on the analysis of socio-psychological factors affecting the state of a person in a group of students will be useful for the activities of the university's psychological services in the process of developing recommendations for creating favorable conditions for the adaptation of students at different stages. training, to optimize the activity of the student group, to optimize the access of the individual to the group, which allows for more effective implementation of educational functions in the profession of vocational education.

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